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2. Research proposal

2a. Proposed research

Group-think in friction: the collective behavior of micro-contacts

I. Introduction

Friction is omnipresent; it is found in many natural phenomena and in many engineering systems, but it also enables something as trivial as walking. It occurs at various length scales from the kilometer scale in the case of earthquakes (the sliding of tectonic plates) to the micro- and nanometer scale in hard drives and other micro- or nano-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS/NEMS) [1–6, Fig. 1]. Friction can have benefits, for example in the case of cycling and tactile sensing, but often it is associated with energy losses and wear. In fact, frictional losses are responsible for a large portion of the world’s energy consumption [7, 8].

Figure 1. Applications.

Given the societal impact it is not surprising that friction has attracted significant research attention dating back to the era of Leonardo da Vinci. Through time, careful experiments have resulted in *simple phenomenological models* that capture the key behavior at the engineering scale (e.g. the *rate-and-state* model, see Box 1 below). Considering its relevance, it may seem surprising that the link to the underlying physics is only partly established [9–11].

The reason for this lack in understanding lies in the fact that friction is inherently multi-scale [12, 13, Fig. 2]. Because each surface is rough, the physical interactions between atoms take place only in a small fraction of the nominal contact surface, at asperities (the local peaks of the interfaces). The physics of these micro-contacts is highly complex, and warrants a multi-physics perspective [Fig. 2(c,d)]. A further complicating factor is that also the bulk materials locally behave highly non-linear. At present, separate (discrete, coupled discrete-continuum, and continuum) computational models are used to understand and homogenize the behavior at this scale [14–20].

Even if these individual micro-contacts would be fully understood and characterized for each material system, still essential mechanisms at the *meso-scale* [Fig. 2(b)] are missing: (i) Roughness profiles are almost always complex, introducing significant statistical complexity involving several length scales [21, 22]. (ii) The surfaces themselves evolve under the influence of the interactions, which introduces velocity and history dependence at the macro-scale [23]. (iii) The micro-contacts have long range interactions through the bulk materials, which causes dynamical effects [24, 25]. These meso-scale mechanisms result in emergent behavior at the macroscopic scale whereby the physics of the micro-contacts are complemented by geometric and statistical effects.

Figure 2. Friction is an inherently multi-scale phenomenon.

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In spite of their importance, many uncertainties prevail related to these *meso-scale mechanisms*. The reason is twofold. First, experimental observations and measurements are barely possible as these mechanisms occur in between materials, never at a free surface. Available experiments use model systems (different materials) in which one of the two materials is transparent [26–30]. Second, from a modeling perspective the computational demands are significant. Most models therefore strongly idealize the geometrical complexity to one or a few regularly spaced smooth asperities [23, 31–34], thereby effectively disregarding the meso-scale effects.

It is not until the present time that *meso-scale computations* are actually possible. Because better hardware and software is available, but mostly because interesting discoveries at the micro-scale enable treating the micro-contacts in a homogenized manner [23, 32, 35–38]. This allows, for the first time, the study of statistically relevant systems.

The starting point of this proposal is a recent meso-scale study by Hulikal et al. [39]. They show that the history dependence at the macro-scale can be explained by the collective behavior of the micro-contacts. Hulikal et al. [39] simplified the surfaces as being rigid; ignored the interactions between the micro-contacts all together; and finally, modeled the micro-contacts similar to the macroscopic, phenomenological, models. *The proposed research addresses all shortcomings, to gain a deeper understanding of the origin of the macro-scale phenomena.*

A fundamental understanding of the meso-scale mechanisms of friction will establish the missing connection between the phenomenological models at the macro-scale and the physics of the contacts at the micro-scale. This will enable predictive engineering, tailoring of interfaces, and mastering friction relations; e.g. to address the energetic losses due to friction. Currently, only careful experimental calibration can be used, whereby potentially important phenomena remain hidden due to the fitting of the measurements to existing models.

II. Goal

The goal of this research is to establish the missing link between the fundamental physical interactions at the smallest length scale and the observed behavior at the (engineering) macro-scale. This will be used to understand and improve macroscopic models, and make new predictions with them. A *meso-scale computational framework* is proposed that will be used to address the following research questions (RQ):

- RQ 1. How are the statistical properties of the roughness profiles related to the properties observed at the macro-scale?
- RQ 2. How do the roughness profiles evolve due to the micro-contacts and the macroscopic loading conditions?
- RQ 3. (*Key contribution*) What is the effect of long-range interactions between the micro-contacts through the bulk materials (*their 'group-think'*)? Is there critical behavior governing the release of micro-contacts?

To reach these objectives:

1. Each RQ builds on the previous one in terms of physical insight and methods.
2. The proposed computational framework will be tailored for high-performance computing by taking advantage of the established codes developed at the host institute and of its computational resources [40].
3. This proposal builds on the broad experience of the host institute in the field of friction [41–46, prestigious ERC starting grant on this topic (2009-2014)].
4. Apart from running the computations, this study necessitates automated and objective statistical analyses, which is the expertise of the applicant.

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Box 1: state-of-the-art in macroscopic models (phenomenological)

At the macroscopic scale, friction is defined by means of static and dynamic friction coefficients (μ_s and μ_k): the ratio of the normal force applied to the surface and the shear force needed to initiate/sustain sliding. The rate-and-state model describes the evolution of the coefficients in time and as a function of the sliding velocity [10, 47].

At zero velocity, friction is expressed through the static friction coefficient μ_s , often observed to increase logarithmically with time:

$$\mu_s = \mu_0 + a \ln(bt + 1)$$

where μ_0 , a , and b are parameters which depend on the bulk materials and the roughness of the surfaces. Thereby a and b determine the rate at which the static friction coefficient μ_s increases, see Fig. (a) below. As observed, it is more difficult to initiate sliding if the surfaces have been in contact for a long time.

The amount of force needed to sustain sliding at a certain velocity is expressed through the kinetic friction coefficient μ_k . It depends on the velocity v and on the sliding history through the state variable θ , which follows an aging law:

$$\mu_k = \mu_0 + a \ln\left(\frac{v}{v_0}\right) + b \ln\left(\frac{v_0 \theta}{L}\right) \quad \text{with} \quad \dot{\theta} = 1 - \frac{v\theta}{L}$$

where μ_0 , a , b , v_0 , and L are parameters that depend on the materials and the surfaces. The ratio a/b determines whether μ_k increases (velocity strengthening) or decreases (velocity weakening) upon an increase of the velocity v . L is the length needed for μ_k to reach a steady-state after a velocity jump. Both effects are shown in Figures (b) and (c), resulting from an instantaneous increase in velocity at t_1

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III. Detailed research plan

RQ 1

To unravel the statistical complexity of the rough surfaces, the effect of the roughness is isolated. To this end, each of the micro-contacts is explicitly accounted for, but the bulk is strongly idealized to behave elastically. This way, the short range (non-linear) interactions of the micro-contacts are accounted for, but they do not interact through the bulk. By assuming that the bodies are in-plane periodic and semi-infinite out-of-plane, an explicit solution can be exploited for the bulk [48]. This so-called *spectral method* treats the problem as a boundary integral. It employs explicit time-integration to compute the response of the bulk, in Fourier space, given certain surface tractions. These surface tractions are the result of the micro-contacts.

Figure 3. Cartoon of the simple multi-scale multi-asperity model. Only those connections where the surfaces are sufficiently close are active (in red). The rest of the connections are modeled but inactive. *NB real model is much more complex, and 3-D [Fig. 4].*

Figure 4. Roughness profiles with different statistical properties [49].

Since the typical length-scale at the modeled meso-scale is much larger than the interatomic spacing we assume separation of scales. This allows us to model the micro-contacts in a continuum sense. Each micro-contact is thereby modeled using Coulomb friction in combination with different constitutive models to model different physical interaction at the micro-scale (elastic, visco-elastic, or elasto-plastic). To simplify the computations, instead of explicitly evaluating whether individual points of the surface are in contact or not, we assume all points of the surfaces to be in contact at all times, and use the separation distance to scale the force to zero when points are out of contact, see Fig. 3.

The final ingredient of the model is the homogenization scheme. Down from the macro- to the meso-scale, the normal force is applied as a pressure load on each of the contacts. Up from the meso- to the macro-scale a simple summation over the interface is used.

The developed computational model is sufficiently efficient to allow the study of many large surfaces with a wide range of statistical properties (e.g. Fig. 4). It has been shown that realistic surfaces can be generated using Gaussian distributions [7, 49], which enable systematic, well-controlled, variations of the different length scales that characterize the roughness.

At this point, a detailed study will be performed to assess the required spatial resolution of the numerical model.

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RQ 2

The surface evolution, however still in a quasi-static way, is introduced through the interaction between the micro-contacts and the bulk. To model the effect, an elasto-plastic model is used for bulk – taken finite in out-of-plane direction. The spectral solver can no longer be used, and we resort to standard finite elements instead (see Fig. 5). This requires more targeted simulations of smaller interfaces, which include only the relevant features (based on the outcomes of RQ 1). Note that these computations are only possible because the micro-contacts are considered in a continuum sense.

The main goal is to identify the physical motivation for the history dependence of the friction coefficients, and the parameters in Box 1. We thus consider ‘quasi-static’ sliding.

Figure 5. Cartoon of the multi-scale multi-asperity model: bulk is elasto-plastic or visco-plastic. Only connections where the surfaces are close are active (thick red line). *NB real model is much more complex, and 3-D [Fig. 4].*

RQ 3 (key contribution)

Here we arrive at the core of this research, which involves the dynamics of sliding surfaces. The fact that all micro-contacts are modeled in a time dependent manner, allows the assessment of the long range interactions between the micro-contacts. Following the above, we commence this investigation by isolating the statistics of the surfaces. Large, complex, surfaces are thereby considered, by restricting the non-linearity to the micro-contacts; allowing the use of the efficient *spectral solver* from RQ 1. With this model at hand, a physical motivation is sought for the phenomena of velocity strengthening and velocity weakening, observed at the macro-scale.

Our focus is then extended to the effect of the dissipation of the bulk. Time dependent (viscous) behavior of the bulk is included, again for simplified surfaces (as this has to be solved by finite elements). The dynamical setting allows the study of the effects of inertia, because the bulk is explicitly modeled.

RQ 3 can now be answered by carefully studying the sequence of events. Does one micro-contact detach causing an avalanche around it? Do multiple contacts detach at the same time? How do new contacts stabilize this? The mechanism that is identified here may be coupled to the characteristic length scale at the macro-scale (L in Box 1). If successful, *this is very novel and can sparkle a wealth of new questions.*

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Overlap with past experience and available methods/implementations

- The spectral method has strong similarities to the the spectral method developed and improved by the applicant [50, 51].
- An implementation of the spectral method is readily available at the host institute [52]. A surface generator and experimentally measured surfaces are also available [42, 49].
- A high-performance finite element code is available at the host institute [40].
- The experience of the applicant with geometrical statistics and large scale computations is vital to extract general insights from multi-dimensional computations [53–56].
- To the expertise of the applicant, objective and automatic analyses will be essential.

IV. Schedule and deliverables

		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8
RQ 1.1	Learn/adapt spectral method								
RQ 1.2	Implement micro-contacts								
RQ 1.3	Compare statistically different surfaces								
RQ 1.4	Write publication 1								
RQ 2.1	Learn/adapt finite element code								
RQ 2.2	Implement micro-contacts								
RQ 2.3	Static friction for different bulk behaviors								
RQ 2.4	Write publication 2								
RQ 3.1	Dynamical analysis								
RQ 3.2	Large systems + parameter variations								
RQ 3.3	Write publication 3 (meso-scale)								
RQ 3.4	Macroscopic modeling								
RQ 3.5	Write publication 4 (macro-scale)								

Deliverables

- Four publications in high-ranking international journals, of which RQ 3.5 has the potential of a Nature or Science publication.
- Four conference abstracts for international conferences.
- Open-source software.

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2b. Literature references

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